

QUICK MARCH OF HUMANITY TO A GLOBAL SOCIETY. WHAT CAN THE MAIN WORLD'S RELIGIONS PROVIDE FOR ATTAINING A FAIR STATE?

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Abstract

Purpose – The paper is aiming to identify and deliniate the content of globalization and the responses of the main world religions facing with the challenges of globalization.

Methodology/approach - The present paper is a bibliographical study of globalization from the perspective of the main world religions.

Findings – Globalization has major political, economic, social, cultural, religious and environmental implications, some beneficial, others detrimental for a good part of individuals, local communities, regions and nations.

Research limitations/implications – The research was limited by the speculative aspect of the approach from the spiritual outlook of Buddhism, Christianity, Islam, Judaism and Hinduism.

Practical implications – Attracting religion to building a "fair" and pluralistic global society can contribute to a better understanding between the followers of the great world religions, and to the genesis of a new ethos of a global society, beneficial for all stakeholders involved in globalization.

Originality/value – The new vision, of a globalization based on competition and not adversity, as main principle of world's order is opening opportunities to religion in providing an important contribution through its set of moral values and through the material and spiritual perspective on the human being.

Key words: globalization, spiritual outlook, world religions

Introduction

Expressed either by several competing but related terms, such as "globalization", "globalism", "globality" [(Beck (2003), Marin (2004)], "mondialisation" [Marin (2004)], or even through one of its extreme forms of "globalution" [Friedman (2001) apud Marin (2004)], or through metaphorical formulations such as "global village", "second modernity" [(Marin, 2004)], "think global, act local" etc., the process that humanity is going through today towards a "global", "postmodern", "post-industrial" or "post-capitalist" society and of course "post-communist" for several European countries and those of the former Soviet Union [Marga (2004), Soros (2002) apud Marin (2004)] is, according to the cited authors, has certain and irreversible course [Bauman (1999), Marin (2004), Dima (2004)].

Based on an extensive bibliographic research, by delineating the key aspects of the "phenomenon of globalization", i.e. tracing its historical milestones, the semantic of the various terms being used, its course of action, and also its impact on political, economic, social, cultural, religious, environmental level, the research results have led to the conclusion of the current transition to a global society, based on new principles and mechanisms of operation [Marin (2004)].

As an ongoing process in which the search for realistic solutions is in full swing, the idea that the world's major religions could provide a contribution, along with other forms of human knowledge and experience in science, technology, philosophy, etc. [Marga (2004)], through their spiritual outlook on world and man, respectively through the moral values they promote, is not to be neglected.

The authors' approach does not prove to be useless, on the one hand, due to the revival of religion, reported by several authors [Kepel (1993), Berger (1999) in Kadir & Maufur (2011), p. 399, (Marga, 2004)], and on the other hand and perhaps even due to this fact, the relationship between religion and the phenomenon of globalization being the subject of several studies and researches, published in the form of books, respectively scientific papers [Grigore (2003); Marga (2004); Beyer (2007); Ranganathananda (2010); Herrington (2013); Roudometof (2014); Juergensmeyer (2014); Miu (2020)], covering a wide range of world religions: Judaism, Christianity, Islam, Buddhism, Hinduism, Jainism, Shikism and Zoroastrianism.

Globalization. A brief literature review

The first main section of the paper contains answers to a set of key questions on the subject, that are referring to issues as to when has globalization begun and how can we define it? If there are several competing terms that are circumscribed to the phenomenon of globalization, and what are the differences in their semantic content? What are the characteristics and manifestations of globalization and what actors are behind it? What is the constellation of the consequences associated with the phenomenon of globalization?

Turning now to tracing the origins of globalization in time, the interest on the subject, arouse by several scholars and researchers, gave valuable syntheses. So, Steger divides the history of globalization into 5 periods: prehistoric (10,000 - 3,500 B.C.E.); premodern (3,500 B.C.E. - 1,500 C.E.), early modern (1,500 - 1,750 C.E.), modern (1,750 - 1,970) and contemporary (from 1970 onwards) [Steger (2003)]. In turn, criticizing the approaches that reduce the beginnings of globalization to the present times, categorized as "presentism" and an "Euro-centrist" vision, marked by "the rise of the West", which neglects the evolutions of the non-European world, Pieterse proposes a palette of perspectives for the periodization of globalization, which takes into account the unit of analysis, as a key variable of analysis, but also the time horizon of the perspective, that of "Breitsicht" and "Langsicht" [(Elias (1994) , in Pieterse (2012)]. Thus, the outlook may target globalization as "part of planetary evolution (4000-3000 B.C.E.); as a commercial revolution (ca. 1000 B.C.E.); as a world economy (taking shape at 500 C.E., 1100, 1200 or 1500); as modernity (starting with 1800); and as a recent trend (the 1960s)" [Pieterse (2012), p. 17]. Finally, a group of Russian authors proposes, based on the combination of the "connectivist" approach with the "institutional" one, as "phases" of the history of globalization: archaic, proto-modern, early modern, modern and postmodern [Zinkina (2019), p 225].

The second aspect of interest in the bibliographic synthesis that makes the subject of this section of the article is, on the one hand, to identify a comprehensive definition of globalization, and on the other hand, to capture the competing terms, together with the presentation of their differences in semantic content. In terms of definitions, the bibliographic study undertaken by the authors showed a multitude of formulations, which makes it difficult for those who try to identify a comprehensive definition. On this line of investigation, in the only extensive analysis of the definitions of globalization, elaborated by Al-Rodhan and Stoudmann, shows that the diversity of perspectives from which globalization can be defined or interpreted is determined by the "individual's political ideology, geographic location, social status, cultural background, and ethnic and religious affiliation" [Al-Rodhan & Stoudmann (2006), p. 3]. Moreover, the same authors argue that the diversity of points of view in defining globalization also reflects the perspective of the areas of interest: economic, social, political, etc. Continuing Kumar's line of thought [Kumar (2003), apud Al-Rodhan & Stoudmann (2006)], Al-Rodhan and Stoudmann emphasize that the criterion for validating the definition of globalization is, ultimately, its ability to capture reality. So, Al-Rodhan and Stoudmann provide an integrative definition capturing the causes, development and consequences of globalization, from the perspective of several human activities ("linguistic, cultural, economic, political") and non-human aspects ("bird flu, as well as natural disasters such as tornadoes, tsunamis, earthquakes, and hurricanes") [Al-Rodhan & Stoudmann (2006), pp. 5-6].

Going further, globalization benefits from a number of competing terms, which sweep, in terms of their semantic content, the whole range of positive, neutral or negative connotations. For example, Marin distinguishes between "globalution" (with a negative connotation and understood as "a process of ex-stretching from the center to the periphery of the values of the single global model, in the sense of external revolution, import of standards by which innovation becomes preeminent over tradition and forces modernization as cultural uniformity" [Marin (2004), p. 18]); "globality" (with neutral connotation, which "captures nationally constructed interdependencies,...., a form of internationalism, [having] as

working method intergovernmental cooperation [and at the same time] a solution that preserves state sovereignty" [Marin (2004), p. 20]); "globalism" (with a negative connotation, belonging to the "notional class of imperialism, as a formula of force endorsed by the principle of adversity, [in the deviant forms of] mondialization and hegemony, [promoting] the production model, as a model of success, and a way of life of cultural and behavioral typification" [Marin (2004), p. 21]; "globalization" (positive connotation), which the author considers rather a prone stage of human history [Marin (2004), pp. 23-26], whose characteristics will be the subject of analysis in the following sections of the article.

Other competing terms of globalization, encountered in the bibliographical research have more or less metaphorical formulations, such as "global village" [McLuhan (1997) apud Marin (2004)], "the second modernity" [Marin (2004)], "global", "postmodern", "post-industrial", or "post-capitalist" society [Marga (2004), Marin (2004), Tofană (2007)], "glocalization" [Robertson (1995); Roudometof (2014)], "westernization", "Americanization", or even "McDonaldization" [Kadir & Maufur (2011), p.397], "deceptive face of universality" [Mantzaris (2002), p.6].

The approach to the complex phenomenon of globalization reveals a multitude of "facets" or perspectives from which it can be seen, approaches that also present overlapping areas. Thus, Steger talks about the economic, political, cultural and ideological dimensions [Steger (2003)], while Makhoul develops the aspects derived from "the politics, the economics, the sociology and the psychology of globalization", proposing an integrated model of understanding it [Makhoul (2014)].

We will further deal with the presentation of the relevant aspects of globalization following the definition proposed by Al-Rodhan & Stoudmann [Al-Rodhan & Stoudmann (2006)], which encompasses causes, processes and consequences. So, the bibliographic study reveals that at the root of the complex phenomenon of globalization are laying multiple causes, of a very diversified nature. Thus we can talk about political causes (global and regional agreements between states) [Makhoul (2014)], politico-military (NATO alliance) [Dima (2004)], politico-institutional (International Monetary Fund, the World Bank, World Trade Organization, Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, etc.), technological (unparalleled progress in human history in the fields of communication and transport technology - a cause unanimously reported by authors), economic (liberalization of markets for goods, services and of capital) [Garrett (2000)], the expansion of the great world religions [Herrington (2013)].

Certainly, between the causes and effects of globalization are laying the processes that took place, and the agents that stood behind. Starting with the agents of globalization, Marin differentiates between "global institutions: the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, the Bank for International Settlements, the World Trade Organization, the United Nations Group of Developed Countries, the World Health Organization" [Marin (2004), p.71] and "global factors (agencies): global firms, hypermarkets, risk funds, virtual space operators, non-governmental organizations, associations of intellectual environments and spiritual practices, bodies of international standards, personalities of global notoriety" [Marin (2004), p.75].

Finally, another analysis portrays the "process of mondialization" by "the global nature of science and technology, global marketing, the global financial system, communications infrastructure and the global institutional framework" [Bran & John (2009), p. 48], and distinguish between the "dimensions of globalization": "the economic dimension, highlighted by neoliberal measures, the power of multinational companies and the institutional involvement of the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund"; "the political globalization, highlighted by the individualization of institutions and supra-territorial associations, united by the same norms and interests"; and the "ideological globalization, seen as a system of ideas shared on a large scale, beliefs, norms, values and ideals accepted as valid, true, by a group of people". The identified five major ideologies related to the process of globalization are "liberalization and global market integration; its inevitable and irreversible character; no one is responsible for the phenomenon of globalization; everyone benefits from it; it contributes to the spread of democracy in the world" [Bran & Ioan (2009), pp. 51-56].

The consequences of globalization represent perhaps the fiercest field debated in the voluminous body of studies and research dedicated to the phenomenon, from a wide range of perspectives: political, military, economic, social, cultural, religious, ecological, etc. They are both positive and negative, Al-Rodhan and Stoudmann emphasizing "the ambivalence of the impact of globalization on security and stability, both individually and collectively (globally)" [Al-Rodhan & Stoudmann (2006), p. 6]. In economic terms, for example, globalization have created "winners and losers" [Kadir & Maufur (2011), p. 395]. Of course, advocates of globalization will argue that the beneficial effects prevail, while opponents will

argue that the situation is the other way around. Thus, in the chapter that takes up the rhetorical question in the title of his book, whether "globalization is good or bad" Nicholas Dima introduces the labels of "globalists of the market" for its proponents, respectively, "globalists of justice" and "nationalists" or patriots", for its opponents. Those in the first category, "support free and unrestricted international trade and worship consumerism; ... [argue that] the traditional state is a temporary arrangement that must be abolished; ... globalization is inevitable and irreversible, ... it propagates democracy and benefits everyone, ... if not now, then in the future", and in a concentrated form, taken from Business Week (1999), "globalization represents the triumph of markets over governments" [Dima (2004), pp. 116-117]. Opponents of globalization on the other hand, accuse "the disparities and social polarization caused by globalization, [which] is bad because it enriches a small minority and impoverishes the majority; advocate an equitable redistribution of the wealth of power between the states of the world, by establishing a new economic policy [(Steger (2003) in Dima (2004), p. 117; Dima (2004), pp. 116-117). They have also established the World Social Forum, in response to the World Economic Forum. Last but not the least, "nationalists" or "patriots seek to preserve the nation-state and its prerogatives, ..., believe in God and defend respect for national traditions" [Dima (2004), pp. 116-117].

In another condensed and well balanced synthesis on the "facets of globalization" presented above, Makhoul lists among the positive effects of globalization, "the reduction in the prices of consumer and capital goods, the free movement of capital, rationalization of production, the emergence of global brands, an increase in the world gross domestic product (GDP), reduction in income inequality between high and low income countries, bringing down the barriers to the transfer of technology". Among the negative ones, the author enumerates "benefits from globalization are not shared equally between all trading partners, workers in the old industrialized countries lose their jobs, the increase in the power of multinational firms, the struggle of infant industries in developing countries for survival, currency manipulation tactics to increase products' competitive advantages in the global market, continuation of some of the advanced countries' barriers to the import of agricultural and other products" [Makhoul (2014), p. 61].

For his part, in his analysis based upon statistical data on the "distributive consequences" of globalization, though limited only to the economic perspective of the "international integration of markets for goods, services and capital," Garrett lists the "increasing the income gap between rich and poor countries, income inequality within nations, volatility in economic activity, and with it, economic insecurity among citizens" and "reducing the capacity of the state to redistribute wealth and risk" [Garrett (2001), p. 1].

Our synthesis cannot be widowed by the social, cultural and ecological aspects, which will be touched on anyway, but only tangentially in the second part of the article, because the discussion about religion and globalization cannot avoid them. Beyond the space limitations of the article, we must emphasize, however, as Harrington rightly points out, the discourse on globalization is "economic-centric" and "western-centric", hence the perception of non-Western cultures of the process of "westernization", as a cultural dimension of globalization" [Harrington (2013), p. 146].

So, at the social level, the "financial and economic liberalization, the processes of restructuring, mergers and acquisitions, mediated mainly by Transnational Companies (TNCs), have led to the closure of enterprises, ..., globalization has added tens of millions of people to the unemployed, thus contributing to accentuating poverty" [Bran & Ioan (2009), pp. 56-57]. Moreover, globalization led to the segregation between "center and periphery", in which the beneficiaries of globalization enjoy "global mobility" as an expression of "freedom of movement", while at the antipodes, the poor have to endure "their imprisonment in the locality" [Bauman (1999), p. 6]. These negative aspects of globalization are confirmed by perhaps the most knowledgeable author of studies on its consequences, who is the former chief economist and vice president of the World Bank, Joseph Stiglitz, who speaks of "the devastating effect that globalization has on countries in development and especially on the poor populations of these countries" [Stiglitz (2005), pp. 9-10].

Finally, analyzes of the relationship between globalization and the environment reveal complex interactions on multiple possible levels of analysis (economic, knowledge, and governance) [Najan et al. (2007), in Bran & John (2009), pp. 75]. After Stead and Stead, economic growth is accompanied by population growth, the two leading to increased production but also consumption, which naturally lead on the one hand to depletion of resources and increased pollution, and hence the wide range of adverse consequences on the environment: climate change, wetland loss, ozone depletion, deforestation, species extinction, acid rains, human health problems and reduced quality of life, and environmental

and political activism [Stead & Stead (1996), Bran & Ioan (2009), pp. 63]. Finally, Bran and Ioan present four perspectives from which the globalization-environment relationship can be viewed: the liberal perspective (argues that economic growth, in terms of production and consumption, will generate high incomes ultimately leading to improved environmental conditions); the institutionalist perspective (promotes the idea of the need to increase institutional and regulatory power at global and national level); the ecological perspective ("globalization promotes economic growth, but contributes to environmental degradation by universalizing the Western model of consumption"); the green socialist perspective ("supports the strengthening the autonomy of local communities, ..., capitalism being the main cause of social and environmental injustice, weakens the authority of the local community and imposes the domination of Western cultural paradigms, emphasizes the domination of rich and marginalized women, indigenous peoples and poor") [Bran & Ioan (2009), pp. 146-149].

Summarizing what is shown in the sub-section dedicated to the consequences of globalization, we can say, that they are multiple. Besides the salient advancements in communication and transportation technologies, making the world a "global village", we cannot overlook also its drawbacks, of a political nature, among which we mention on one hand the loss of power of nation states over TNCs, respectively the partial loss of sovereignty in the face of new forms of association between states (as in the case of the European Union) [Dima (2004)]; those of an economic and social nature [Bauman (1999), Stiglitz (2005)], shown in more detail above; those on the environment [Bran & Ioan (2009)], or the cultural ones [Tomlison (2002), Cârjă (2012)]. However, resuming Dima's rhetorical question, "is globalization good or bad?" [Dima (2004)], we would like to emphasize Stiglitz's statement that "globalization must not be abandoned", this being "not feasible or desirable. It is not globalization that is the problem, but the way it has unfolded so far" [Stiglitz (2005), pp. 329-340], the author proposing in the same time a reform plan, including the creation of international public institutions. Perhaps more answers will come from the analysis of the relationship between religion and globalization, which we will discuss in the next section.

Religion in the face of globalization

The study of the interplay between religion and globalization is gaining an increasing interest among scholars and researchers and we believe that there are a number of arguments to justify this upward trend. Firstly, according to the 2015 PEW Research Center Report, adherents of the world's major religions were approx. 5.7 billion, including here only the Christians, Muslims, Hindus, Buddhists, Jews, which means that out of a total of approx. 7.8 billion of the world's population today, 73% of the planet's inhabitants belong to a certain religion, a fact not to be neglected. Secondly, there are studies that are taking into account among the dimensions of globalization, the religion and culture, along with new technologies in the fields of communication and transport, the political and military, and of course, economic and environmental [Stahl (2007), pp. 336-339, in Kadir & Maufur (2011), p. 396]. Thirdly, despite the lack of attention from sociological theories to aspects of religion, as a component part of the complex phenomenon of globalization, prevailing its political, economic and military aspects (Turner (2007), pp. 345- 348, in Kadir & Maufur (2011), p. 396], perhaps and in the same time due to the focus of sociologists' attention almost exclusively on the topic of secularization [Roudmetof (2014), p. 151], one can identify a trend in countercurrent, that of desecularization, or a revival of religion [Kepel (1993), Berger (1999) in Kadir & Maufur (2011), p. 399], and contrary to modernity's predictions of "its exit from history", according to Hegel, Ferbach, Marx, Comte, Nietzsche [Marga (2004), p.9]. This is also demonstrated by the fact that in the post-communist and post-capitalist phase, people no longer identify with the ideology they were attracted to before, but in addition to nationality - which itself undergoes transformations in the case of emigrants - identity their is rather ethnic and religious [Kadir & Maufur (2011), p. 401]. Fourth, there is a parallelism between the journey of religion in the history of humanity and the history of globalization, its action as a driving force, but also as an opponent of globalization, which outlines according to Herrington a paradoxical relationship of "agent - opponent" one [Herrington (2013), pp. 145].

Given the above arguments regarding the rationality of debating the topic of the interaction between religion and globalization, we intend to answer, in delineating this topic, a few questions as to what is religion and how do the world's major religions relate to the challenges of modernism and globalization?

Overcoming the lack of general consensus on the generic definition of religion pointed out by Beyer, understood as "some reference to supraempirical beings or transcendent dimensions beyond the everyday world of the five senses", things become much more concrete in the case of "institutionalized religions" [Beyer (2008), pp. 444]. However, we provide a neutral definition from the Merriam-Webster dictionary, which states two meanings: "(1) the service and worship of God or the supernatural and (2)

commitment or devotion to religious faith or observance" [<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/religion>].

It should also be noted that the analysis of the phenomenon of secularization in recent decades has been accompanied or maybe generated by a reluctant attitude especially in the corporate environment to use the term religion with the meaning of an "institutionalized religion" in favor of spirituality, considered as being less ritualistic and not belonging to a specific religious doctrine [Lungu & Lungu (2012)].

Regarding the second aspect, of the way the main world religions are relating to the phenomenon of globalization, the bibliographic study pointed out both common and specific elements, the latter belonging to their specific spiritual outlook towards humans and world (see Table 1), but never overlooking both beneficial and detrimental aspects of the process of globalization, most of them identified in the above more "secular" studies and researches.

Discussion, conclusions, limitations and further research

Reviewing what has been shown so far, we emphasize that globalization is a complex phenomenon, considered by some as inevitable, natural and irreversible [Bran & Ioan (2009)], while others perceive it as an economic expression of the "New World Order" [Dima (2004), pp. 116; pp. 9]. Then, seen from a historical perspective, globalization seems to have its origins in ancient times, and there can be isolated distinct phases or stages, among which the last decades are characterized by the most accelerated dynamics.

Apart from its used terms and definitions, this paper has first outlined, the causes, processes, actors and consequences of globalization, according to various authors. It was highlighted that the phenomenon of globalization can be analyzed from a multitude of points of view, including political, military, economic, social, cultural, ecological demographic, etc.

A second goal of this paper was to analyze how the world's major religions relate to the phenomenon of globalization. Due to the inherent space limitations, but also of the time constrains devoted to the bibliographic research, the paper was limited to only five of the major world religions, namely Buddhism, Christianity, Islam, Judaism, and Hinduism (in alphabetical order), following as in the future the analysis should be extended to other religions.

In the debate on the interaction between religion and globalization, the authors were interested in identifying the beneficial and harmful elements of globalization for humanity, respectively, from the perspective of the spiritual outlook of each religion. Here, an extensive analysis would go far beyond the scope of a single article.

The innovative element that this article brings with, is the identified niches in which religion, or "institutionalized religions" [Beyer (2008)] can intervene in structuring a "fair" globalization for all parties involved. In this endeavor, it was particularly useful for us to differentiate between the two "principles of world order" [Marin (2004)], one based on adversity, in which "one part tries to impose itself by force on the whole"; the second, based on competition, in which "the whole is more than the sum of the parts" [Marin (2004)]. Starting from this point forward, one can outline the idea of a globalization based on the second principle, which allows to imagine a vision, as a state of the future, in which religions find ways to contribute to building a "global society", through the set of moral values they promote and through the dichotomous perspective on the human being, material and spiritual. Such a vision is ultimately what was promoted by the famous Catholic theologian, Hans Küng, who advocated a new ethos of the world, an ethos that would be reflected on all three coordinates political, economic and scientific [Küng (2000, 2002, 2004) in Marga (2008)] of a "global society". No less true is that such an approach would also contribute to the rapprochement of religions that would be involved in a common effort to build a "fair" and "pluralistic" global society, taking into account their common ground, but also each specificity. In our opinion, this reconciliation should go beyond the paradigm of the "Jerusalem, Athens, Rome triangle, for healing the neuroses of history" [Marga (2008)], in a broad sense. We are not overlooking here also the intra-confessional cleavages (in the case of Christianity between the Orthodox, Roman-Catholic and Protestant Churches, among Shiites and Sunnis in the Islamic world and perhaps not so pronounced between Reformed, Orthodox, and Conservative Judaism). It remains for this thesis to be deepened and elaborated in the future. A development of Marin Marin's Thesis about globalization resting on two

principles of world order stated above [Marin (2004)], by incorporating authors' vision on integrating religion in the process of globalization for attaining a fair state is presented in Fig. 1.

Table 1. The benefits and detriments of globalization from the main world religions' outlook

Religion	Benefits	Detriments
<i>Christianity</i>	Fostering rapprochement between people and facilitating communication by removing dividing barriers [Mantzaridis (2002), p.6]; internationalization of scientific research results, expansion of communications worldwide, dissolution of economic protectionism [Tofană (2007), p.7]	The homogenization of the world and the loss of the concept of man as a person, the rule of money [Mantzaridis (2002), p.7]; „the annihilation of the personal diversity of individuals, the leveling of traditional cultures, the particularity of Christian spirituality and the removal of any trace of eschatological responsibility, individually or in community” [Tofană (2007), p.10]
<i>Buddhism</i>	Modernity brought „impressive achievements ... in transport, communication, electronics, health, human rights”; [Dhammananda (2010), p.58]	Though increase in material and physical welfare development the decay of morality and spirituality reflected in our behavior to the environment, wars and cruelty to our fellows, all attributable to greed [Dhammananda (2010), p.58]
<i>Islam</i>	Integration of time and space, .., increasingly reduced importance of the 'imaginary boundaries' of state territories ('global village'), ..., intensified and accelerated religious and cultural exchange among people, making them interdependent to each other” [Kadir & Maufur (2011), p.397]; Through globalization religion filled the economic gap between developed and developing countries and led to “the unsecularization of the world” or “the revival of global religion”, ..., generated a stronger feeling of religiosity than nation-states [Kadir & Maufur (2011), p.399]	Threat of cultural homogenization and imposing the western style of life to non western civilization; less impact in rural areas than in urban ones [Engineer (2010), pp.91-101]; Globalization promoted „certain ideologies like capitalism (McDonaldization or Americanization), ..., it is imperialism of the Capitalism of the West (like colonization and its new forms), ..., is rooted in modernity and neo-liberalism that follow from the greedy-Western philosophy, immorality, individualism and capitalist domination” [Kadir & Maufur (2011), pp.397-401]
<i>Judaism</i>	Globalization provides with “unprecedented opportunity” [Odenheimer (2009)]; Due to „Internet, satellite television, computers, cell phones, email and out-sourcing, the world became smaller and more interconnected than ever before in its history” [Schulweis (2004)]	Globalization is promoting a „market centered vision of social life”, in which „ politically powerful multinational corporations control and dominate the world’s economy”; impoverishing the „farmers living in semi-communal villages [that] have been forced off their land by a combination of violence, trickery, and the degradation of their environment and have been forced to sell their labor to factories, mining companies, or plantation owners”; plundering the developing countries of their non renewable resources, accompanied by a devastating pollution and environment damage; globalization led to „maximizing the accumulation of wealth by multinational corporations”, knowing that „concentration of wealth that inevitably leads to abuses of power” [and] „the nexus of political and economic power that perverts justice in order to serve the greed of the wealthy” [Odenheimer (2009)]
<i>Hinduism</i>	„Greater affluence, better communication and advancements in technology”; „global advancement in science, technology and business”; attainability for well educated persons in getting jobs in developed countries; increased „planetary” consciousness [Shastri (2010), pp.79-90],	Damaging effects on environment (but also the rise of the concern for it from the part of the opponents of globalization), poverty of vulnerable nations, increasing gap between rich and poor, cultural homogenization instead respect for culture diversity, new form of colonialism („continued projection of western and European civilization and its values for everyone”), „misuse of Hindu tolerance” from the part of Christianity and Islam; promotion of a materialistic way of life, a culture penetrated by sex and violence and offering false human models (athletes and movie stars), promotion of the thesis of „clash of cultures” as a threat against multiculturalism, “cultural chauvinism and isolationism” [Shastri (2010), pp.79-90]

Fig.1. A transition model from globalism towards globalization

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